

Image Text to Speech Translator in Specified Language

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Abstract: This innovative application offers a seamless multilingual experience, initiated by capturing images for swift text extraction. Upon text recognition, effortless translations are available in languages such as Kannada, Telugu, Hindi, Tamil, Marathi, Urdu and extended to languages like French, Spanish, and Japanese. Inclusivity is enhanced through audio renditions of translations, benefiting visually impaired users. This integrated tool acts as a language bridge, fostering efficient cross-lingual communication and understanding. An invaluable asset for users aiming for rapid and accurate inter-language interactions, the application signifies a ground-breaking approach to breaking language barriers while accommodating diverse linguistic needs.

Keywords: Image, Text, Speech, Conversion ,Extraction, Image Processing

I. INTRODUCTION

The intersection of convolutional neural network (CNN) and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) has birthed innovative technologies in recent years, with broad applications in assistive technology, accessibility, and education. Our research is dedicated to refining and expanding existing methods to develop an image text-to-speech conversion system. This system aims to accurately extract text from images and offer users the freedom to select their preferred language for synthesized speech output.

Numerous mobile applications have emerged to aid reading and support individuals with visual impairments. Similarly, communicating with someone who speaks a different language poses significant challenges, often requiring expensive translation services. The creation of image text-to-speech (ITTS) conversion systems addresses this challenge by enabling the conversion of image text into spoken content, benefiting language learners, visually impaired individuals, and those engaging with textual content.

Our proposed work, centered on an Android-based image text-to-speech conversion system, seeks to enhance accessibility and meet diverse user needs. By seamlessly integrating convolutional neural network (CNN) and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) on a popular mobile platform, we aim to offer a practical and customizable solution. Key metrics, including text extraction accuracy, speech synthesis responsiveness, and language customization effectiveness, are rigorously evaluated. Moreover, user feedback and usability testing inform continual refinements to optimize the application for real-world use.

Mobile phones have become indispensable tools for communication in our digital society, facilitating calls and text messaging with ease. Recognizing verbal communication as the most efficient means of delivering information, text-to-speech (TTS) services were initially developed to aid the visually impaired. Our focus lies in leveraging Optical Character Recognition for text-to-speech conversion, aiming to enhance assistance for individuals more efficiently

II.LITERATURESURVEY

- 1. Muhammad Ajmal; Farooq Ahmad; Martinez-Enriquez A.M.; Mudasser Naseer; Aslam Muhammad; Mohsin Ashraf ;Image to Multilingual Text Conversion for Literacy Education;17-20December 2018.** Currently, language and visuals collaborate to bolster literacy instruction while also playing pivotal roles in the texts we engage with. This research project focuses on developing an application that integrates text translation with visuals to promote visual literacy. Additionally, a comprehensive review of diverse methods for multilingual image-to-text translation is undertaken. Building upon this review, an enhanced methodology is proposed to address identified gaps in the literature. Consequently, the construction of the application involves four primary stages: capture, extraction, recognition, and translation. Specifically, the Optical Character Recognition method is employed to ensure high-accuracy character extraction and recognition across various environmental conditions. Users can effortlessly translate text by simply capturing an image with their smartphone camera, enabling real-time language selection on their mobile device.
- 2. H.Waruna H.Premachandra Information Communication Technology Center, Wayamba University of SriLanka, Makandura, SriLanka; Anuradha Jayakody; Hiroharu Kawanaka; Converting high resolution multilingual printed document images into editable text using image processing and artificial intelligence;12-13 March**

2022. predominantly handwritten or printed text on paper, undergoes transformation into an editable electronic format through the process of optical character recognition (OCR). Literature indicates that only a handful of OCR systems possess the capability to accurately discern multilingual characters, such as those blending English and Sinhala. The primary challenge addressed in this study revolves around the lack of suitable technology for identifying multilingual text, a persisting issue demanding attention from the scientific community at large. The overarching objective of this project is to develop a bilingual character recognition system adept at simultaneously recognizing printed Sinhala and English scripts, leveraging artificial neural networks and character image geometry properties. The roadmap involves augmenting the solution to encompass the three most prevalent languages in Sri Lanka, with Tamil slated for inclusion in a subsequent update. Artificial Neural Networks and character geometry features serve as the primary technological pillars underpinning this investigation. Leveraging a database comprising over 800 images, categorized into 46 characters (20 Sinhala and 26 English), with each character represented by 20 distinct images, the project has achieved an approximate success rate of 85% thus far.

- 3. Nikolaos Bourbakis; Image understanding for converting images into natural language text sentences; 21-23August2010.** A summary is provided, yet the realms of knowledge discovery, document interpretation, human-computer interaction, and other disciplines stand to reap immense benefits from the adept processing, correlation, and comprehension of multimedia-based events or multi-modal information. In tackling this pivotal challenge, the creation of a unified platform emerges as a strategic endeavor, seamlessly integrating various modalities such as text and graphics into a cohesive medium and interlinking them to facilitate effective processing and understanding. This session delves into the development of a system harnessing image processing-analysis techniques and attribute-laden graphs for object detection and picture comprehension. Its core functionality revolves around automatically translating photos into natural language (NL) text sentences, subsequently transforming these NL text sentences into graph representations. Furthermore, it introduces a methodology for converting NL sentences into graph representations, which are further refined into descriptions using Stochastic Petri-nets (SPN). This approach not only furnishes a common model for representing multimodal data but also enables the association of

"activities or changes" in image frames, facilitating the representation and interpretation of events.

- 4. CongMa; Yaping Zhang; MeiTu; XuHan; Linghui Wu;YangZhao;YuZhou; Improving End-to-End Text Image Translation From the Auxiliary Text Translation Task; 21-25 August2022** In recent studies, considerable attention has been directed towards end-to-end text image translation (TIT), aiming to translate the source language embedded in images into the desired target language. However, the effectiveness of end-to-end text picture translation is hampered by the scarcity of data. To address this challenge, multi-task learning emerges as a non-trivial solution, involving the exploration of knowledge from related tasks that complement each other. In this study, we propose a novel approach to text translation augmented text picture translation, wherein text translation serves as an auxiliary task to train the end-to-end model. Leveraging multi-task training and parameter sharing, our method maximizes the utilization of abundant large-scale text parallel corpora readily available. Extensive experimental results demonstrate that our proposed approach outperforms existing end-to-end methods. Moreover, joint multi-task learning incorporating both text translation and recognition tasks yields superior outcomes, showcasing the complementary nature of translation and recognition auxiliary tasks.

III.METHODOLOGY

Fig 1:Proposed Diagram

Fig 2: Block Diagram for Working Principle

In the image text-to-speech conversion process for desired languages, optical character recognition (OCR) for text extraction from images and text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis for transforming the extracted text into spoken words are pivotal stages. Here's a comprehensive methodology for implementing this process:

- 1. Selecting an OCR Tool/API:** Choose an OCR library or API capable of accurately extracting text from images and supporting multiple languages. Options include Tesseract OCR, Google Cloud Vision API, and Microsoft Azure Computer Vision API.
- 2. Image Preprocessing:** Enhance text extraction quality by preprocessing input images. Techniques like resizing, noise reduction, and contrast adjustment can optimize image quality.
- 3. Text Extraction:** Utilize the selected OCR tool to extract text from preprocessed images. Ensure language compatibility for precise identification.
- 4. Language Configuration:** Configure the TTS system to accurately pronounce words by detecting or specifying the language.
- 5. Image Processing:** Extracting letters from images and converting them into a digital format for recitation involves image processing techniques. These techniques entail applying a series of functions to the image format to derive specific information. Initially, the image is loaded and converted into grayscale, where pixel values fall within a defined range. This

range aids in identifying individual letters, with whitespace typically represented by white pixels.

6. Speech Generation: Feed the extracted text into the TTS system to generate appropriate speech output. Verify that the chosen TTS system produces natural-sounding speech and supports the desired language.

7. User Interface and Interaction:

- **Designing User Interface:** Develop a user-friendly interface enabling users to select languages, upload images, and initiate the text-to-speech conversion.
- **User Language Preferences:** Allow users to choose the language for speech synthesis and text extraction.
- **Integration with Platforms:** Incorporate the image text-to-speech feature into user preferences and customization sections.
- **User Preferences:** Enhance user experience by enabling adjustments to speech preferences like voice pitch, speed, and volume.
- **Personalization:** Implement user profiles to store customization options, such as language preferences, for a tailored experience.

IV.RESULTS

Fig 4.1 Initial Frontend Xml Design For The App

Fig 4.2: English to Kannada

Fig 4.3: English to Tamil

Fig 4.4: English to Telugu

Fig 4.5: English to Hindi

Fig 4.6: English to Urdu

Fig 4.7: English to Spanish

Fig 4.8: English to French

Fig 4.9: English to Japanese

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this innovative application transcends language barriers by seamlessly integrating image-based text extraction, effortless translations, and audio support. It offers a transformative solution for diverse linguistic needs, promoting inclusive communication. By acting as a language bridge, the application paves the way for efficient cross-lingual interactions, marking a remarkable breakthrough in breaking language barriers.

VI.FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

Future enhancements for this application could involve expanding the language repertoire, incorporating real-time translation capabilities, and integrating AI-driven improvements for text recognition accuracy. Further, continuous accessibility enhancements for visually impaired users, along with user-friendly interface refinements, will contribute to a more comprehensive and user-centric multilingual experience.

VII.REFERENCES

- [1]. Muhammad Ajmal; Farooq Ahmad; Martinez-Enriquez A.M.; MudasserNaseer; Aslam Muhammad; Mohsin Ashraf ;Image to Multilingual Text Conversion for Literacy Education ; 17-20 December 2018.
- [2]. H.Waruna H. Premachandra Information Communication Technology Center, Wayamba University of Sri Lanka, Makandura, Sri Lanka ; AnuradhaJayakody; HiroharuKawanaka; Converting high resolution multilingual printed document images in to editable text using image processing and artificial intelligence; 12-13 March 2022.
- [3]. NikolaosBourbakis ;Image understanding for converting images into natural language text sentences; 21- 23 August 2010.
- [4]. Cong Ma; Yaping Zhang; Mei Tu; Xu Han; Linghui Wu; Yang Zhao; Yu Zhou ;Improving End-to-End Text Image Translation From the Auxiliary Text Translation Task; 21-25 August 2022
- [5]. Fai Wong; Sam Chao; Wai Kit Chan; Yi Ping Li; Recognition of Chinese character in snapshot translation system; 23-25 November 2010.

- [6] Victor Fragoso, Steffen Gauglitz, Shane Zamora, Jim Kleban, Matthew Turk “TranslatAR: A Mobile Augmented Reality Translator”2010 IEEE.
- [7] Ariffin Abdul Muthalib¹, Anas Abdelsatar¹, Mohammad Salameh¹, Juhriyansyah Dalle² “Making Learning Ubiquitous With Mobile Translator Using Optical Character Recognition (OCR)” 2011 ICACISIS.
- [8] Shalin A. Chopra¹, Amit A. Ghadge², Onkar A. Padwal³, Karan S. Punjabi⁴, Prof. Gandhali S. Gurjar⁵ “ Optical Character Recognition” International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 3, Issue 1, January 2014.
- [9] Hideharu Nakajima, Yoshihiro Matsuo, Masaaki Nagata, Kuniko Saito “Portable Translator Capable of Recognizing Characters on Signboard and Menu Captured by Built-in Camera” 2005 Association for Computational Linguistics/Proceedings of the ACL Interactive Poster and Demonstration Sessions, pages 61– 64, Ann Arbor, June 2005..
- [10] Nag, S., Ganguly, P. K., Roy, S., Jha, S., Bose, K., Jha, A., & Dasgupta, K. (2018). Offline Extraction of Indic Regional Language from Natural Scene Image using Text Segmentation and Deep Convolutional Sequence. arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.06208.